

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN SHAPING YOUTH’S NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Abstract: *Education develops a country’s economy and society; therefore, it is the milestone of a nation’s development. Education provides knowledge and skills to the population, as well as shaping the personality of the youth of a nation.*

Key words: *education, ethnic group, personality, national identity, youth.*

Education develops a country’s economy and society; therefore, it is the milestone of a nation’s development. Education provides knowledge and skills to the population, as well as shaping the personality of the youth of a nation. Nevertheless, can education shape the youth’s national identity? Can education cultivate the person's identity or sense of belonging to the nation?

Education is very important for an individual's success in life. It can give a big impact on human opportunity in continuing their life quality. Education is generally seen as the foundation of society which brings economic wealth, social prosperity and political stability. Economic and social status depends on education obtained by individual since education contributes to individual capability in managing quality of life. It can help one’s individual to avoid from poverty, build up harmony and democracy society. Education also capable to give power for them to voice out their views, expose to them their real potential, lead them to become a better person and widen their views in certain area.

Education is the key to move in the world, seek better jobs and ultimately succeed in life. Education is the best investment for the people because well educated people have more opportunities to get a job which gives them satisfaction. Educated individuals enjoy respect among their colleagues and they can effectively contribute to the development of their country and society by inventing new devices and discoveries. Main purpose of education is to educate individuals within society, to prepare and qualify them for work in economy as well as to integrate people into society and teach them values and morals of society. Role of education is means of socializing individuals and to keep society smoothing and remain stable. Education in society prepares youngsters for adulthood so that they may form the next generation of leaders. One of the education essential tasks is to enable people to understand themselves. Students must be equipped with knowledge and skills which are needed to participate effectively as member of society and contribute towards the development of shared values and common identity.

Education can be regarded as systematic efforts that build up by the society in order to deliver the knowledge, value, attitude and skill among their group members towards an

effort to enhance individual's potential and changes that occurred in themselves. This definition is consistent with Education Philosophy whereby "Education in Malaysia is an on-going effort towards further developing the potential of individuals in a holistic and integrated manner, so as to produce individuals who are intellectually, spiritually, emotionally and physically balanced and harmonic, based on a firm belief in and devotion to God. Such an effort is designed to produce Malaysian citizens who are knowledgeable and competent, who possess high moral standards and who are responsible and capable of achieving high level of personal well-being as well as being able to contribute to the harmony and betterment of the family, the society and the nation at large".

National identity is formed by a society that exists in it. Thus, all the science of education both in terms of skills, academic and personal is very important to the country in forming the personality of youth today. Education received by students is what shapes the identity of the country where education have a substantial impact on life opportunities to acquire good quality and identity. Therefore, quality education is a dynamic concept of change and evolves over time and changes in the context of social, economic and environmental. According to Ross and Wu (1996), education level of individuals incapable of managing the quality of life for economic and social development depends on the education received. Through education, individuals can build self-esteem among them the confidence to face the world and society and to understand the heart's desire. Wehmeyer (1996) states that self-assertiveness is the foundation of one's life. With firmness, individuals are capable of making choices and decisions on actions and break free from outside influence or interference that is not beneficial. Assertiveness and confidence is a knowledge derived from education. Without education, ones self-esteem is not as strong as a person who acquires knowledge in education.

Obviously education has a very important role in transmitting and fostering values that determine, in turn, behaviours, attitudes, reactions specific of responsible citizens. According to Deni Hardianto (2005), failure of education in shaping the national identity is due to the components in the education system. All members of society including teacher, educational facilities and government's commitment need to get involved in improving education. For instance teachers also must have a strong identity and at the same time strong commitment in cultivating the sense of identity to the students. The government needs to play an important role in the development of national education. It includes provide adequate education, take care of teacher's welfare and avoid making education as a political medium.

As a conclusion, education plays a significant role in achieving a good quality of life. It is because education is importance guidance in human's life. It can be regarded as important medium in changing the paradigm shift in one's individual. Generally, education is always associated with the process of delivering skill, disseminating knowledge and internalizing value. Practically, individual who equipped with knowledge can be able to internalize and apply the knowledge in everyday's life. In children's context, education can be seen as continuing process of their development, so that they can practice and apply their knowledge as preparation in the future. Thus, education is

major aspect of development of any modern society since if there is a deficit of educated people then society will stop its further progress.

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